

Diving into Extended Phase Graph-based Deep Learning for Accurate and Fast T2 Mapping with PENGUIN

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Quantitative Magnetic Resonance Imaging often suffers from time-consuming parameter fitting operations, preventing its use in routine clinical evaluation. Model-based deep learning networks can push acceleration rates by incorporating the MR signal model into the learning process to estimate parametric maps of the tissues, alleviating the need for extensive training datasets. However, most of the previously proposed methods are limited to employing a pure exponential curve to model the MR signal, which does not account for stimulated or indirect echoes, or inhomogeneity of the B1 field, in order to avoid the time-consuming calculation of a more complex signal model. Here, the PhasE graph sigNals and Gradients qUantitative Inference machiNe (PENGUIN) method is proposed, which adapts the Recurrent Inference Machine (RIM) implemented by Sabidussi et al. [1] (model-based method), to perform T2 mapping of brain regions with a more accurate signal model based on the Extended Phase Graphs (EPG) concept [2], while also attempting to estimate the effective B1 field to improve the T2 map estimate. PENGUIN takes advantage of a pre-calculated dictionary of MR signal evolution curves and corresponding gradients for a combination of T2 and B1 values to avoid their calculation during training and inference of the network, thus speeding up the estimation.

METHODS: A dictionary of echo-modulation curves based on the EPG formulation and corresponding gradients was built for T2 = 0:1:2000 ms, B1 = 0.6:0.01:1.4, and T1 = 1000 ms, following a multi echo spin-echo (ME-SE) acquisition sequence, with 32 echoes, TE=10:10:320 ms and flip angle FA = [180°, 160°, ... 160°]. The RIM portion of the network followed the configuration adopted by Sabidussi et al. [1]. PENGUIN was trained with fully synthetic data from 10 BrainWeb's discrete anatomical images [3], split into a total of 72 000 patches, from which a set of ground-truth T2 and B1 maps and corresponding T2-weighted images were simulated by looking up the dictionaries. PENGUIN was tested on *in vivo* images of a healthy subject previously acquired in a Philips Achieva 3T scanner, imaging 6 slices with spatial resolution of 1.6×1.6×4.0 mm³, field-of-view 250×250 mm², and repetition time 4 s.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: PENGUIN estimates a 320×320 pixel map in 4±0.1 s, 380-fold faster than a RIM implemented with the EPG signal model, and 465-fold faster than a pattern-recognition approach sharing the same dictionary. The T2 maps estimated with PENGUIN in *in vivo* images have a maximum median difference of 2.8 ms in the brain parenchyma compared to those obtained with the pattern recognition approach. Even taking these errors into account, PENGUIN is still 25-fold faster than a patter-recognition approach with a T2 dictionary step of 2 ms.

Figure 1: (A) PENGUIN configuration. (B) T2 maps estimated from *in vivo* weighted images, each column corresponding to a different slice, with the pattern recognition approach with 1 ms T2 dictionary step (top) and with PENGUIN (middle), and difference map between them (bottom). The median error (in ms) was calculated in the brain parenchyma region, excluding the CSF.

References

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